

Reactions of Portugal on the Liberation of Portuguese Territories in India in a Historical Perspective

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ABSTRACT

After a prolong stay in India both Portuguese and French showed their disinterest to leave India after its independence. After a series of discussion and deliberations, French decided to leave India where as Portuguese continued to dishonor the talks and deliberations. The Initiative of India in Liberating Portuguese enclaves in India was appreciated and condemned by many countries and leaders of the world. Like any other defeated countries in the battle, Portugal condemned and criticized this act of India. Lisbon also mourned the loss of Goa and described it as “the fall of our civilization’s biggest and dearest symbol”. A historian, Salmas Calando, told the Geographical Society of Lisbon, “The fall of Goa marks a return into the darkness that ousted before Vasco da Gama arrived there in 1498”. To these problems, even after liberation there arose an administrative challenge which also developed a silent and growing tension between the force of national integration and religious exclusiveness, with the government of India actively supporting the latter cause become a promise once made during the freedom movement days to maintain a center of Portuguese culture in Goa, as French in Pondicherry. History, religion, and politics have got mixed up in Goa so much so that is attracting more attention than is warranted by actual circumstances. Laws and customs which are part of the social pattern of these areas and which are consistent with fundamental human rights and freedom will be respected and modifications will be sought only by negotiation and consent.

Key Words: Portuguese culture, Geographical Society, Goa marks, Liberating Portuguese

Introduction

One of the three most important events faced by our national leaders immediately after the independence was Partition of British India into India and Pakistan, Integration of states on lines and finally liberation of Portuguese territories in India. After a prolong stay in India both Portuguese and French showed their disinterest to leave India after its independence. After a series of discussion and deliberations, French decided to leave India where as Portuguese continued to dishonor the talks and deliberations. When hopes on discussion and deliberations brought nothing, India and its leader Jawaharlal Nehru decided to convince Portugal to leave India through non-violence menace code named as Operation Vijay and liberated Portuguese territories in India on 29 December 1961.

Liberating Portuguese enclaves in India

The Initiative of India in Liberating Portuguese enclaves in India was appreciated and condemned by many countries and leaders of the world. But its quite interesting to note the reactions of Portugal after loosing its enclaves in battle field in few hours.

Like any other defeated countries in the battle, Portugal condemned and criticized this act of India. Lisbon also mourned the loss of Goa and described it as “the fall of our civilization’s biggest and dearest symbol”. The usual pre-Christmas festivities gave way to bitterness as student demonstrators chanted “Goa is ours,” “Goa is Portuguese” and “Glory to the armed forces.” A historian, Dr. Salmas Calando, told the Geographical Society of Lisbon, “The fall of Goa marks a return into the darkness that ousted before Vasco da Gama arrived there in 1498”. Portugal did not celebrate the New Year “on account of, the loss of Goa.” On the eve of New Year, President Amenco Tomas told the people that “it is to be expected that the West will finally awake from the lethargy in which it has been living, realizing that it may be rapidly walking towards the worst of all slaveries”.

On January 3, 1962, Dr. Salazar told the National Assembly that one of the missions of the 3,500 Portuguese troops in Portuguese India was to force the Indian Union to set afoot, a large military operation which would shock the world and that this mission had been fulfilled.

Dr. Salazar issued a threat that the Portuguese might decide to leave the U.N., which had not come to its aid when appealed to. Portugal refused to accept India’s “occupation of Goa” as an accomplished fact. He paid tributes to Britain and the U. S. for their efforts in New Delhi to try

to prevent India from using force in Goa but regretted their impotence in the matter. He also paid tributes to the solidarity shown in the case of Goa by Brazil and Spain and the request made in New Delhi by Canada, Australia, West Germany, Argentina, Belgium, and Holland, to mention only those of which he had direct knowledge. “Difficulties will arise for both sides when the programme of Indianization of Goa begins to clash with the Goans and when the Prime Minister discovers that a definite individuality has been formed there down the centuries by interpenetration of cultures and by the crossing of various races.”ⁱ On the other hand, on February 3, 1962, the Portuguese National Assembly unanimously approved a Government Bill by which Portugal formally refused to recognize Indian sovereignty over Goa, Daman, and Diu. According to this Bill, who maintains all political and administrative institutions created by Portugal, Goa would continue to be represented in the Assembly by their representatives of Goan origin. The Bill provides that for the time being all Goan officers or organizations appointed by Portugal will have their headquarters in Lisbon. Within hours of Dr. Salazar’s attack on Great Britain, London retorted. Mr. S.W. Roskill, Britain’s official Naval Historian said that Portugal was in no position to complain about Britain’s lukewarm attitude in supporting it over Goa because Portugal was tardy in supporting Britain in World War II. Mr. Roskill said in a letter to The Times, “It is pertinent to remind our Portuguese friends that they did not rush to Britain’s aid in 1939, nor even in 1940 when we stood alone against Hitler and Mussolini and sorely needed the use of the naval and air bases on the coast of Portugal.

Produced by the Portuguese Government

Furthermore, it took two years of patient, many people at the time felt too patient negotiation with Dr. Salazar before, on August 18, 1943, he signed an agreement permitting us to use bases in the Azores, from which the central Atlantic could be cleared of U-boats. And even then, so many difficulties were produced by the Portuguese Government regarding American participation in those facilities that it was not until October 1943, that the agreement became effective. Portugal, had she stood by the alliance in our time of real need, could have saved us enormous shipping losses after the end of 1942 at negligible risk to her.” New Delhi also sharply reacted to Dr. Salazar’s speech. It maintained that the statement that Dr. Salazar wanted to force India to take military action in Goa only confirmed the Government of India’s view that a peaceful settlement with the Portuguese was out of the question. The British Government rejected Dr. Salazar’s charge that Britain had used delaying tactics when Portugal requested the use of El Adam (Libya) or Gan (Maldives Islands) Aerodrome for the defence of Goa. A Foreign Office spokesman said that Dr. Salazar’s statement had been misleading because Britain is not able to

grant the use of the bases, the Portuguese had asked for without the permission of the host Governments.ⁱⁱ

Apart from Portugal, even British government reacted sharply instructing Sir Ross to tell the Portuguese that they should at once lodge a complaint against India with the U.N and Britain was ready to support the resolution ‘deploring Indian use of force and demanding the withdrawal of Indian troops occupied Portuguese territories’. On December 18, 1961 Lord Home, the Secretary of State for Foreign Office, summoned T.N. Kaul, the Indian Acting High Commissioner in London and expressed Britain’s dismay at India’s military action in Goa. The Foreign Secretary made it clear that although Britain appreciated the strength of the Indian feeling about Goa, it was a pity that India had chosen to resort to force despite respected Anglo-American representations. He cautioned that such action would damage India’s reputation in the world and set a bad precedent for similar action elsewhere. Mr. Kaul attempted to defend his government’s action stating that Portugal had been reluctant for the last 14 years to solve the problem by peaceful means. And the public opinion on India was completely against the Portuguese presence in Goa. Therefore, India had no other option but to settle the issue once and for all this way. Lord Home, however, still, remained concerned and distressed. Following this Anglo-Indian exchange of views, the Foreign Secretary, on the afternoon of December 18, 1961, made a statement in the parliament deploring the use of force by India and expressing the view that the immediate and urgent step was to arrange for an end to the fighting. Nevertheless, he added that the Portuguese government had ‘not felt disposed to follow the example of Britain and France’ in India.ⁱⁱⁱ

Indian Government made it very clear to the world that “It was in the vital interest of India, therefore, that the world needed to know that India had not unconditionally foresworn the use of force, that it would not hesitate to use armed force in the last resort to resist evil, and that it had not lost the will to fight and defend its rights. India scores don’t consider its military actions in Goa as much of a military feat. That action was no more than a proof of India's will to use force when other methods were exhausted. And that is its only significance in the eyes of the world. Let the world; therefore, make no mistake about India’s pacifism. While India prefers peaceful methods in settling international disputes, it will not flinch from using armed force to back its rights when peaceful methods failed.^{iv} These sentences made it very clear that when India’s request to cooperate in peaceful consumption was turned down by Portuguese. India was

forced to use the armed force.^v Thus the picture presented in the world regarding the state of Indian is not correct.^{vi}

Irrespective of great hatred, the Indian Government made all arrangements for the people who wish to move to Portugal and at the same time, precautions methods were taken to treat the Portuguese officers with respect. This is very clear from the fact when the Governor-General of Goa, Daman, and Diu, General Manuel Antonio Vassalo de Silva, was found by Indian soldiers on the morning of December 20 in a small house in Margao, he and his wife were taken to a larger house and they were accorded the courtesies appropriate to their status. The Indian troops rounded up 201 Portuguese Army Officers, 13 Naval Officers, 19 Police Officers lent to the police force by the Portuguese army, 2,596 other ranks, and 275 policemen. No evidence was found of the Portuguese employing alien troops or Goan soldiers. About 100 Portuguese civilians, including 60 Doctors working in civilian hospitals were permitted to continue their professions in Goa.

The Indian troops also recovered large quantities of dynamite at different places in the settlement, apparently kept for blowing up strategic installations. Because of the speed of the operation, the Portuguese could destroy only a few houses here and there, including the governor's house.

The Ministry stated on January 30, 1962, that Portugal had accepted in principle two Indian suggestions. One was that all Portuguese civilians and military' personnel in Goa, Daman, and Diu, including Goans who regarded themselves Portuguese, should be repatriated. It was agreed that Bombay would be the point of embarkation. Secondly, Portugal should release all Indians interned in its overseas territories, allow them to resume their normal pursuits and retain their assets. The Ministry had previously stated that the Government of India was in contact with the British, U.S. and Brazilian Governments to arrange sea and air transport for the repatriation of the Portuguese in India. Within hours of their arrival, the Indian troops started repairing damaged communication lines within Goa and between Goa and the rest of India. Besides destroying several minor bridges and culverts, the Portuguese had also put out of order three main bridges in Goa to impede the advance of the Indian Army. These were at Bauastarira, eight miles east of Panjim, at Ass Nora, six miles from Dodamarg, on the border, and at Berim, between Moimagao and Ponda. The bridges at Banastarim and Ass Nora were rebuilt.^{vii}

Indian Union tried to rebuild Portuguese territories

In this way, the Indian Union tried to rebuild Portuguese territories and establish an efficient administration for the welfare of the people. With the liberation of Portuguese territories now, the biggest of the question is of the state of Goa among the states of Indian Union. There were differences of opinion and rumors on the annexation of Goa to the state of Mysore or Maharashtra. Regarding this, our Prime Minister very clearly said that “I really do not understand why there is so much excitement over Goa in Mysore and Maharashtra. I have made it perfectly clear that Goa is to remain separate and is not to be very few outside officers there, and they will be chosen for their competence. We can hardly apportion them by number to different States. On, May 20, 1962 in a letter to Shri. Nijalingappa it was said, we feel, and I felt for a long time, that Goa has a certain distinctive personality, and it would be a pity to do anything to take away this distinctive personality. Therefore, we had decided, and we hold to that decision, that Goa should be completely understood because we hold to that firmly and there is no point in trying to agitate against that. It merely means trouble, with no result. And why should there be this hankering for Goa to be merged into this State or that State? I don’t understand it. Goa can develop as it likes within the framework of India and adds to the richness of India on May 22, 1963, at a Public Meeting in Panjim. To these when Mr. Nehru was questioned on May 22, 1963, in the Public conference at Panjim, “Don’t you think that Goa, being a small unit should be merged with Maharashtra with which it is linked for centuries?

He replied that I do not think so. I positively think that Goa should remain a separate unit. Of course, it will be affected by close links with the neighboring areas, states, etc., it is natural, and one does not know what in the distant future might happen. But in the present, purely on merits, I think it should be kept separate. Apart from merits, because of a considerable number of people hereIt is immaterial whether they are a majority or minorityA considerable number here are afraid of being submerged to individuality, if I may say so. I think that it is important that it should be given every chance to preserve itself.^{viii}

Thus, regarding the merger of Goa to any states of Indian Union, Mr. Nehru declared that that merger of Goa with any neighboring state was not desirable at present, and it should not take place yet. Further, he said that it did not matter which party won the majority and formed the government, but the original pledge given to the people that the territory would enjoy a separate status should be honored. Referring to the demand for merger of Goa, Mr. Nehru said that it was there even before liberation and was pressed vigorously afterward. (December 14, 1963: PT I,

Jaipur) I do not think that Roman Catholics alone are against the merger. I know that many others are also not in favor of it. What I said, I think, was that apart from others, forty percent of the people who were Roman Catholic were against it.^{ix} Here Our Prime Minister made the very valuable point that is “the problem in the ex-Portuguese colony is radically different and more difficult than what Indian administrators encountered in the princely states following their merger with the Indian Union”.

The task of overhauling and modernizing the administration of these enclaves and bringing them in line with the rest of India will tax all the patience that imagination and statesmanship of the new administrators. As regards the tiny dots of, Daman and Diu, their ultimate future lies in a merger with the contiguous stage of Gujarat and it is both meaningless and inconvenient to administer this little and place from Panjim.^x In short, we should be very clear, Mr. Nehru said, that “It needs to be made very clear here that no Goan- and on this issue, the Hindus and Christians or anonymous will vote for a merger either with Maharashtra or Mysore. Indeed, if there is one issue on which the two elements in the Goan community find themselves united, it is in their passionate desire to be left alone buy both neighbors, to continue as a separate political and economic entity, with the Konkani language as their common bond.^{xi} But when we talk of a Goan identity conditioned by Portuguese or more correctly.

Administrative challenge

Latin culture, these realities should be kept constantly in mind. A failure to do so only results in making this an emotional issue, something which polarizes the people on communal lines. The result would only harm Goa. Thus, whether Goa is to remain a separate unit or merge with the larger contiguous units of the Indian Union is a matter for the Goan people to decide. To these problems, even after liberation there arose an administrative challenge which also developed a silent and growing tension between the force of national integration and religious exclusiveness, with the government of India actively supporting the latter cause become a promise once (check) made during the freedom movement days to maintain a center of Portuguese culture in Goa, as French in Pondicherry. These promises were made at a time when the government of India hoped to win over the western powers to the idea of freedom of Goa, forgetting that these promises were rendered irrelevant after the

liberation of Goa by the Indian army. History, religion, and politics have got mixed up in Goa so much so that is attracting more attention than is warranted by actual circumstances.^{xii}

Conclusion:

Way back on September 24, 1954, while delivering his speech in Parliament, Nehru made a series of promises to Goans and thereby guaranteed their rights. In his speech he said “I would like to take this opportunity of stating once again some aspects of our basic approach with respect to Goa when it becomes a part of the Indian union:

The freedom and rights guaranteed by the constitution of India and which specifically refer to freedom of conscience, worship, and practice of religion will extend in full measure and in all their implications to these areas. The special circumstances of cultural, social and lingual relations and the sense of a territorial group which history has created will be respected. Laws and customs which are part of the social pattern of these areas and which are consistent with fundamental human rights and freedom will be respected and modifications will be sought only by negotiation and consent.

As we have done in the rest of India, full use will be made of the administrative judicial and other services confident that the return of freedom to and the unity of these areas with the motherland will enable adjustments to be made in harmony with progress and with the desires of the people.^{xiii}

END NOTES:

ⁱ Rao R. P. Portuguese Rule in Goa 1510- 1961.p.196.

ⁱⁱ *Ibid.p202*

ⁱⁱⁱ Rahaman, Habibur. "India's Liberation of Goa and the Anglo-American Attitude." India's Liberation of Goa.

^{iv} Mankekar, D. R. The Goa Action. Bombay.p.9.

^v Nehru on Goa. Delhi.p.61.

^{vi} Demand For Grants. Delhi: Indian Parliament, 1955-56.p.3978.

^{vii} *Ibid.p205.*

^{viii} Kelekar, Ravindra, ed. Nation's Solemn Commitments on Goa.p.8-9.

^{ix} *Ibid.p9.*

^x Mankekar, D. R. The Goa Action.p.32.

^{xi} *Ibid.p.37.*

^{xii} Taper R. (Ed). (1965, May), Goa - A Symposium on the many Facts of Its Territory's Crisis of Transition, Seminar 69.p.18

^{xiii} Nehru on Goa. Delhi.p.60.